

Diphenyltin Diisothiocyanate

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Wada et.al¹ in a communication have described the preparation and properties of several dialkyltin diisothiocyanates (alkyl = methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl or *n*-butyl) and some of their bipyridine and stannoxane complexes. From the results of the infrared spectra it is proposed that the thiocyanate group is bonded through the nitrogen atom to the tin atom giving isothiocyanate structure to these compounds. This note reports the preparation, characterisation and infrared data of the hitherto unknown diphenyltin diisothiocyanate.

The compound has been obtained by refluxing diphenyltin diiodide, prepared by the reported procedure,² with a suspension of excess of freshly prepared dry silver thiocyanate in dry benzene for about thirty minutes. The insoluble silver salts were then filtered off and the residue obtained on removal of the solvent from the filtrate was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°). White shining crystals, m.p. 176-177° were obtained (yield 60%). (Found: % C, 42.3; H, 2.8; N, 6.9; S, 16.8. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₀N₂S₂Sn: C, 43.2; H, 2.6; N, 7.2; S, 16.5).

The compound is soluble in common organic solvents viz., benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, acetone etc. and is stable towards atmospheric moisture. Infrared spectrum of the compound in potassium bromide disc recorded in the range 4000-670 cm⁻¹ gave the following absorption frequencies: 3030w, 2083vs(b), 1938w, 1883vw, 1815vw, 1639vw, 1575w, 1479m, 1429s, 1333w, 1304w, 1263vw, 1193w, 1075m, 1066w, 1001m, 917vw, 854vw, 732vs, 698vs cm⁻¹ (v=very, s=strong, w=weak, m=medium, b=broad). The very strong absorption band observed at 2083 cm⁻¹ is definitely due to -NCS stretching vibration. The position, intensity and shape of the band³ point to an isostructure to the compound.

Attempts to prepare the corresponding diphenylgermanium diisothiocyanate by the interaction of diphenylgermanium dibromide, (prepared by reported procedure)⁴ and silver thiocyanate in an inert solvent resulted in the formation of a highly viscous product which could neither be crystallised nor distilled under reduced pressure. It, however, gave a qualitative test for thiocyanate group and a very strong absorption band in the infrared at

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2033 cm^{-1} corresponding to $-\text{NCS}$ stretching vibration. Since the product also gave a strong broad band at 854cm^{-1} assigned to Ge-O-Ge stretching vibration⁵, it is concluded that diphenylgermanium diisothiocyanate is extremely sensitive to atmospheric moisture and has undergone hydrolysis, yielding a partially hydrolysed polymeric material. Further studies on the subject are in progress and would be communicated in a subsequent publication.

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